

Description of authentic materials in language teaching methodology

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Abstract: Authentic materials provide real-life examples of language used in everyday situations. They can be used to add more interest for the learner. They can serve as a reminder to learners that there is an entire population who use the target language in their everyday lives. Authentic materials can provide information about the target culture and provide that culture's perspective on an issue or event. The rich language found in authentic materials provides a source of input language learners need for acquisition.

Key words: language skills, traditional education, authentic, didactic tools, productive skills, language structure

In the first quarter of the 21st century, that is, at the peak of the development of the technical age, the role of foreign languages has been strengthened as a result of progress in various spheres of society, and the demand for it is increasing every hour. It is no secret that the main demand of the labor market of advanced countries facing the world is personnel who can communicate freely in a foreign language, are familiar with computer technologies, are rich in innovative ideas and have their own style. Such requirements, in turn, form the main basis of the educational reforms being carried out in our country. Today, the use of authentic materials in teaching foreign languages is an effective, but methodical method that requires experience.

The word "authentic" comes from the ancient Greek (authentikos) meaning "original, true". In the 1983 edition of the Russian-Uzbek dictionary, the translation of the word "authentic" is given as "true to the original, corresponding to the original, corresponding; the same, equal, true to the original". This word is not given in dictionaries published in subsequent years. Therefore, this concept, which is called "authentic" in English, is called "authentic" in Uzbek, as in many languages. In language learning, the concept of "authentic" means the property of language and speech material that ensures the implementation of speech communication in real life. Authentic material, regardless of what kind of information it is, whether it is text, video or audio material, is not created for the purpose of teaching a language. Therefore, an authentic text is understood as a text written for native speakers and not aimed at educational purposes. However, in modern methods of foreign language teaching, it is considered possible to use materials and texts intended for language learners, specially created or processed by methodologists. The famous linguist J. Harmer emphasizes that finding authentic materials that language learners can master is an important task of education. If this is not possible, he believes that it is better to use adapted materials than materials assembled from different parts. It is known that the lower the level of language proficiency of language learners, the more difficult it is to introduce authentic material into classes and create speech situations. However, using only non-authentic, that is, "artificial" texts also distances learners from the language environment, and the likelihood of creating a real communication situation with the help of such texts is very low. Non-authentic texts are called "adapted" materials, and in most cases, in the process of working on reading comprehension, listening comprehension, writing and speaking skills, the language learner is required

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to master topics and lexical units that are not needed and are not used in real, living language. They also have their place in language learning.

Therefore, in language learning, along with authentic texts, non-authentic texts should also be used depending on the educational goal. However, it is important that all of them are selected in accordance with the speech competence of language learners, and that they provide them with understandable and simply structured models of the language being studied, both orally and in writing. A well-known scientist in the field of applied linguistics and language education, G. Widdowson, introduced the concepts of “authentic material” and “pedagogically authentic material” into science and showed the difference between them. In his opinion, materials that are created for native speakers and have not undergone any changes are considered authentic, original materials. Pedagogically authentic materials, on the other hand, are intended for those who are learning a language as a foreign language, and therefore are adapted to everyday, specific needs for use in classes. Widdowson believes that when choosing materials to be used in classes, it is necessary to simplify them, observing a number of conditions, so that they are easier to understand and master. This material should be original, authentic, and taken from real sources

The concept of “authentic material” has a broad meaning, and this term refers to materials taken from various sources. Therefore, the issue of classifying authentic materials is of great importance in methodology. Russian researchers A.V. Perunova and M.V. Perunov classify authentic materials as follows:

1. Authentic audiovisual materials (television clips, reports, documentaries, advertising).
2. Authentic visual materials (slides, photographs, paintings, road signs, illustrations in magazines, postcards, picture books).
3. Authentic printed materials (newspaper articles, popular materials, song lyrics, restaurant and cafe menus, tourist information brochures, shopping receipts, travel tickets, theater, cinema, concert tickets, business cards, comics, public transport timetables, etc.).
4. Realities (coins and currency, wall clocks, telephones, dolls, marionettes, etc.).

They are used in the educational process mainly as a visual aid or in role-playing situations. Such a classification helps methodologists in selecting authentic materials and using them purposefully and effectively in the educational process. Language realities play a special role in these materials. In addition, S. Vlahov and S. Florin also gave their own explanations and definitions. According to their definition, “realities are words (word combinations) that designate objects that are characteristic of the life (life, culture, social and historical development) of one people and are alien to other peoples”. (Vlahov, S.I.; Florin, S.P. (2009). Untranslatable in translation. Moscow: «R. Valent». 360 p.)

It is difficult to imagine authentic materials without realities. Therefore, the selective use of original, authentic sources in the linguistic-political approach is important. K.S. Krichevskaya includes authentic materials as original works of art, painting, and music, as well as objects found around us. In addition, she separates advertisements, counters, shopping receipts, and the like that we see every day in everyday life into a separate group and calls them pragmatic materials. (Krichevskaya, K.S. (1996). Pragmatic materials that introduce students to the culture and environment of the inhabitants of the country of the language being studied // Foreign languages in school. No. 1. 13-17.) This group also includes audio and audiovisual materials (radio announcements and broadcasts, television programs). She noted that this group of pragmatic materials is useful in the educational process, as it

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reflects modern language models. Another important aspect of authentic materials is that they reflect the changes taking place in the language. Both the teacher and the language learners are aware of every innovation. Also, a certain part of authentic material can be used in different situations if the educational goals are different, which is explained by their universality. Books, articles, newspapers contain different texts and language styles, while textbook educational materials have few such features.

The scientist Ter-Minasova, who has conducted fruitful research on the methods of teaching foreign languages, emphasizes that modern language learners now view language not as a scientific theoretical phenomenon, but as a vital necessity. It is obvious that the current approach and views on learning a foreign language support a method of education rich in real life examples, based on real reality. Many scientists in this regard emphasize the need to pay attention to improving a foreign language using many means of teaching a foreign language - radio broadcasts, the social network Facebook. In foreign studies, the following groups of authentic texts can be found:

- semi-authentic texts, i.e. texts based on the original source, but adapted to the educational program in terms of lexical and syntactic terms;
- roughly-tuned authentic texts, i.e. texts with a level of grammatical material slightly higher than the level of language learners;
- texts with authentic qualities (authentic-looking texts);
- learner authentic texts.

The last group of texts mentioned above attracts the most attention of researchers. Educational-authentic texts (texts with authentic elements and intended for teaching a foreign language in educational institutions) are most often used in the methodology. An example of them is texts adapted using authentic texts in order to determine the level of language proficiency of students. Such texts are classified by Y.V. Nosonovich and R.P. Milrud divided it into 7 different sections:

- 1) culturological texts create an idea of the characteristics of another culture, the customs and lifestyle of the speakers of this culture and language;
- 2) informational texts provide information that is appropriate for the interests and age characteristics of language learners;
- 3) situational texts provide language learners with the naturalness of the situation presented as an educational exhibition and require its discussion;
- 4) texts specific to the national mentality serve to explain the appropriate or inappropriate use of certain sentences and speech units in the language being studied in conversation and communication;
- 5) when developing fast-understanding (reactive) educational texts, it is necessary to take into account their ability to evoke the same authentic speech, thinking and emotional reaction in language learners;
- 6) authentic texts serve to attract the attention of language learners and facilitate their understanding of the communicative function of the text and its relevance to reality;
- 7) authentic educational tasks are text-related tasks that serve to ensure the interaction of language learners with the text. In addition, the tasks should be based on working with sources that occur outside the learning situation.

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